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Fatal accidents at work in Europe

Between 2010 and 2020 they decreased by 23.72% on average for the countries considered

The Eurostat calculates the value of fatal accidents at work. The indicator measures the number of fatal accidents that occur at work and lead to the death of the victim within one year from the accident. The incidence rate refers to the number of fatal accidents for 100,000 employment people. An accident at work is an event that takes place during the work that leads to physical or mental damage. This includes all accidents in the course of work, whether they occur inside or outside the employer's premises, accidents in public places or different means of transport during a trip during the work-commute accidents are excluded - and at home-like during teleworking. It also includes cases of acute poisoning and intentional acts of other people if these have happened during the work.

Ranking of European countries for the value of fatal accidents at work in 2020. Cyprus is in the first place for the value of fatal accidents at work in 2020 with an amount of 4.45 units, followed by Bulgaria with an amount of 3.68 units and by the Italy with an amount of 3.39 units. In the middle of the standings there are Slovenia with 1.85 units, followed by Ireland with a value of 1.79 units and by Estonia with a value of 1.73 units. Germany closes the ranking with an amount of 0.73 units, followed by Sweden with an amount of 0.49 units and by the Netherlands with a value of 0.3 units. It should be noted that Italy is the only one among the large European countries to have a very high level of fatal accidents in the workplace.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the percentage variation of fatal accidents at work between 2010 and 2020. Malta is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of fatal accidents at work between 2010 and 2020 with an amount of 67.76% equal to a variation of 1.24 units, followed by Greece with a value of +20.55% equal to an amount of 0.15 units, and from Croatia with an amount of 17.96% equal to an amount of 0, 44 units. In the middle of the standings there are Norway with an amount of -14.71% equal to a value of -0.25 units, followed by Lithuania with a value of -21.14% equal to an amount of -0.85 units e from Romania with a value of -32.59% equal to a value of -1.60 units. Sweden's ranking close with a value of -60.16% equal to an amount of -0.74 units, followed by Poland with a value of -63.01% equal to an amount of -2.30 units, and come on Netherlands with a value of -65.91% equal to an amount of -0.58 units. Between 2010 and 2020 the percentage value of fatal accidents at work has decreased -23.72%.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Two Clusters are identified or:

- Cluster 1: Finland, Denmark, Switzerland, Norway, Germany, Greece, Sweden, Poland, Iceland, the Netherlands, Belgium, Slovakia, Spain, Cyprus, Hungary, Ireland, Slovenia, Italy, Malta, Czech Republic;
- Cluster 2: Lithuania, Latvia, Bulgaria, Romania, Portugal, Austria, Luxembourg, France, Croatia; Estonia.

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From the median point of view, the Cluster 2 is higher than the Cluster 1. In particular $C2 = 2.63 > C1 = 1.47$.

Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is presented below with the use of the Euclidean distance. Two structures are identified with complex networks or:

- There is a connection between the Czech Republic and Italy with a value of 0.5 units;
- There is a connection between Italy and the Czech Republic for an amount of 0.5 units and between Italy and Spain with a value of 0.58 units;
- Spain has a connection with Italy for an amount of 0.58 units, with Ireland for an amount of 0.55 units and with Hungary for an amount of 0.5 units;
- Hungary has a connection with Spain for an amount of 0.5 units;
- Ireland has a connection with Spain for an amount of 0.55 units and with Slovenia for an amount of 0.61 units;
- Slovenia has a connection with Ireland for an amount of 0.61 units.

There is a complex network structure composed of the following elements or:

- Denmark has a connection with Finland for an amount of 0.6 units;
- Finland has a connection with Denmark and Germany for an amount of 0.56 units;
- Germany has a connection with Finland for an amount of 0.56 units, with Sweden for an amount of 0.38 units and with Greece for an amount of 0.58 units;
- Greece has a connection with Germany for an amount of 0.58 units and with Sweden for an amount of 0.57 units;
- Sweden has a connection with Germany for an amount of 0.38 units and with Greece for an amount of 0.57 units.

Conclusions. Between 2010 and 2020 the average value of fatal accidents in the workplace decreased by 23.72% on average. However, there are countries for which this value grew significantly in the same period as, for example, in the case of Malta with +67.76%, Greece +20.55%, and Croatia with +17.96%. Generally the value of fatal accidents in the workplace tends to decrease with the growth of pro-capita income. However, France and Austria are an exception with a high level of fatal accidents and included in the same clusters as countries with reduced pro-capita income. It should be considered that in general the reduction of fatal accidents in the workplace tends to be associated with the development of the service sector in the European economy. In fact, with the growing of pro-capita income, workers employed in agriculture, industry and buildings are reduced, which are the sectors in which the probability of undergoing a fatal accident in the workplace is greater. However, it is very likely that in the future the value of fatal accidents in the workplace increases due to the European reindustrialization produced by the Mix of Sino-American tension, growth of energy costs and devaluation of the euro due to anti-covid expansive economic policies.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Rank	Country	2010	2020	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Country	2010	2020	Var Ass	Var Per
1	Malta	1,83	3,07	1,24	67,76	16	Romania	4,91	3,31	-1,60	-32,59
2	Greece	0,73	0,88	0,15	20,55	17	Slovenia	2,77	1,85	-0,92	-33,21
3	Croatia	2,45	2,89	0,44	17,96	18	Portugal	4,1	2,72	-1,38	-33,66
4	Italy	3,09	3,39	0,30	9,71	19	Finland	1,51	0,95	-0,56	-37,09
5	France	2,36	2,54	0,18	7,63	20	Hungary	2,61	1,63	-0,98	-37,55
6	Bulgaria	3,6	3,68	0,08	2,22	21	Germany	1,2	0,73	-0,47	-39,17
7	Spain	2,19	2,06	-0,13	-5,94	22	Belgium	2,25	1,33	-0,92	-40,89
8	Czechia	2,48	2,3	-0,18	-7,26	23	Estonia	3,24	1,73	-1,51	-46,60
9	Cyprus	4,93	4,45	-0,48	-9,74	24	Austria	4,44	2,36	-2,08	-46,85

10	Latvia	2,74	2,47	-0,27	-9,85	25	Switzerland	2,13	1,08	-1,05	-49,30
11	Denmark	1,53	1,34	-0,19	-12,42	26	Luxembourg	3,82	1,71	-2,11	-55,24
12	Norway	1,7	1,45	-0,25	-14,71	27	Sweden	1,23	0,49	-0,74	-60,16
13	Lithuania	4,02	3,17	-0,85	-21,14	28	Poland	3,65	1,35	-2,30	-63,01
14	Ireland	2,27	1,79	-0,48	-21,15	29	Netherlands	0,88	0,3	-0,58	-65,91
15	Slovakia	2,04	1,49	-0,55	-26,96						

Rank	Country	2020	Rank	Country	2020
1	Cyprus	4,45	16	Estonia	1,73
2	Bulgaria	3,68	17	Luxembourg	1,71
3	Italy	3,39	18	Hungary	1,63
4	Romania	3,31	19	Iceland	1,54
5	Lithuania	3,17	20	Slovakia	1,49
6	Malta	3,07	21	Norway	1,45
7	Croatia	2,89	22	Poland	1,35
8	Portugal	2,72	23	Denmark	1,34
9	France	2,54	24	Belgium	1,33
10	Latvia	2,47	25	Switzerland	1,08
11	Austria	2,36	26	Finland	0,95
12	Czechia	2,3	27	Greece	0,88
13	Spain	2,06	28	Germany	0,73
14	Slovenia	1,85	29	Sweden	0,49
15	Ireland	1,79	30	Netherlands	0,3

